

Diacritic Restoration in the Serbo-Croatian Macro-Language: diacritic-stripped writing (*šišana*) as a written register and an on-device task

Ilya Osipov

Cubios, Inc. · independent researcher · ilya@ctrl8.com · ORCID: 0000-0002-8017-8153

Preprint, version 7 (full, extended) · 14 June 2026 · language: English

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.20688770** · <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20688770>

Status. This is a preprint: a full, deliberately detailed text, not condensed to the format of any particular journal. It records not only the research argument but also the engineering system, the algorithm, the dictionary-build recipes, and the methodological lessons — so that the work can be understood, reproduced, and ported to other languages. Section 4 (the user survey, Study 1b) describes **planned but not-yet-conducted** work and is clearly separated from the completed corpus results.

Software availability. The restoration engine is released as the open-source, AI-free library **ioDiacritics** (MIT) — the software artifact of this study. Every number in the text was read from the pinned commit `be745a6` (2026-06-13): <https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics/tree/be745a653605f6934ea127f1c2c909e242055b5d>. Runnable demos (SwiftUI and C++ Dear ImGui): <https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics-Demos> (commit `bf392d3`). For a citable identifier, this exact state will additionally be archived as a tagged release with a Zenodo DOI **10.5281/zenodo.20688770**. The same library is embedded by the author in two macOS end-user applications: **PolyType** (an adaptive keyboard / input aid) and **SlipWay** (a clipboard manager forked from **DrPaste**, <https://github.com/ilya000/DrPaste>) through its stateless `str → str` contract.

Declaration of interests. The library, the evaluation harness, and the aggregate results are open-source (MIT), and the study is fully reproducible from open data; the library itself is not a commercial product. The only interest to declare is that the same author develops the two applications named above, which embed the library. This does not bear on the research: every reported number was produced by scripts on open data, none was taken from prior literature, and the validation corpora are independent of the dictionary source.

Abstract

When typing, speakers of Serbo-Croatian routinely strip the Latin diacritics (*č, ć, š, ž, đ*) and reduce text to bare ASCII — a phenomenon known as *ošišana latinica* ("shaved Latin"), or *šišana* for short; we call the inverse operation *dešišavanje* (restoration). The orthography is a digraphia (Cyrillic and Latin used in parallel), and the shaved Latin register sits beside both. We provide evidence that this is neither corruption nor illiteracy but a stable written **register**, induced by the input infrastructure and the communicative environment. Across eight corpora we quantify a register gradient (from ~0% dropped diacritics in edited news to 45% on a technical forum), demonstrate bimodality — text is written in a "with-diacritics" or "without" mode, not mixed — record the selective dropping of *đ*, show orthogonality to standardness, and replicate decade-old observations, establishing the phenomenon's stability. We then formalize the inverse task and show that, with a residual error below the noise floor of real input, it is solvable **on-device, with no neural model at runtime**: by a dictionary with a frequency prior, at an edit-precision of 99.6–99.98%. The central result is a **symmetric experiment**: under a controlled comparison the three varieties of the macro-language (Serbian, Croatian, Bosnian) are indistinguishable in quality; the gap that looked "linguistic" turns out to be a function of dictionary size and the presence of a disambiguation (resolve) table, while a single engine — with no core change — serves the whole continuum. We describe a working open-source implementation (ioDiacritics) and two applications that embed it, draw implications for input-system design, delimit honestly how far the method transfers to neighbouring languages, and lay out the user survey that will complete the HCI part of the work.

Keywords: diacritic restoration; shaved Latin; Serbo-Croatian macro-language; written registers; on-device processing; privacy; HCI; computer-mediated communication.

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1. Introduction

Serbo-Croatian lives under a synchronic digraphia: Cyrillic and Latin are used in parallel, and a literate speaker switches freely between them. On top of that duality a third, de facto form of writing emerges — Latin stripped of its diacritics. When a user types *Cacak* instead of *Čačak*, or *zelim* instead of *želim*, they are usually not making a mistake: they are writing in a form that is instantly legible to the reader and that costs no effort for characters absent from their keyboard layout or slow to enter. The form is so widespread that the question "how often is it used" yields to a sharper one — "under what conditions is it *not* used".

We argue that *šišana* deserves the status of a **register** — a systematic, situation-bound choice of form, not a random deviation from the norm. This thesis has direct design consequences: if dropping diacritics is a conscious register, then an input system has no right to silently "correct" it; it should *offer* restoration, and do so such that a wrong edit does not erode trust. And once that is granted, an engineering question follows: how well, and by what means, can diacritics be restored at all — and is a heavy model needed for it.

The reframe on which the whole work rests: this is **not error correction but intent restoration**. The writer knew the correct form and dropped the marks because of the input environment, not out of ignorance. Three principles follow, governing every design and evaluation choice below: (1) never touch a foreign-language token in code-switched text; (2) never override the writing mode the user chose; (3) the cost of a wrong edit far exceeds the cost of a miss — **precision-first**.

The work makes three connected contributions. **Sociolinguistic** (Study 1, §3): we quantify the prevalence and structure of *šišana* and justify its register status — through a genre gradient, bimodality, and replication over time. **Computational** (§6–§8): we describe the anatomy of the restoration task, its principled ceiling, and the structural reason naive methods break on mixed (foreign-language) input, and we show the task is solvable on-device. **Systemic and typological** (§8–§10): we demonstrate that a single engine serves the entire Serbo-Croatian macro-language (ISO 639-3 *hbs*), describe a working privacy-preserving system, and carefully delimit where the method transfers and where it does not.

The thesis tying the three contributions together is simple: diacritic reduction is a property of the writing environment and the diasystem, not of an individual language standard; its inversion is a computationally tractable task best defined at the level of the macro-language. The Montenegrin case (§11.2), in which a politically singled-out variety turns out to be computationally indistinguishable from Serbian, is a miniature illustration of this thesis. The framing is deliberately **operational and neutral**: *hbs* is a technical label, variety exclusions are made on a computational criterion rather than on a judgment of language status, and the data and UI for each variety are kept separate. This matters because the status of Serbo-Croatian ("one macro-language with variants" vs. "separate languages") is perceived differently in Belgrade, Sarajevo, and Banja Luka.

2. Background and related work

Serbo-Croatian digraphia has long been described (Magner 2001; Hentschel 1998): Cyrillic and Latin coexist as two full-fledged orthographies of one language, in strict correspondence under Vuk's alphabet, where the three Latin digraphs *lj*, *nj*, *dž* map to the single Cyrillic letters *љ*, *њ*, *џ*. Less studied is the third layer — the systematic dropping of diacritics in digital communication.

The closest predecessor to our work is Ivković (2013, 2015), who, on two news platforms with manual coding, established the very existence of the phenomenon and its ideological loading (share of messages without diacritics: 71% on B92, 56.5% on Politika) and proposed a "technology-driven" framing of the writing. Ivković laid the foundation — existence and ideology on two single-genre sites. Our contribution relative to his lies on a different plane: scale and register coverage (eight sources instead of two, from news to technical forums), an automatic measurement method instead of manual coding, a proof of the phenomenon's discreteness

(bimodality, §3.5), and a decade-later replication showing the register is stable rather than transitional.

On the language-processing side, diacritic restoration has been studied as an applied task, and we build on this work without re-appropriating its results. Šantić, Šnajder & Bašić (2009) for Croatian: dictionary-only 97%, with a bigram language model 98.81%. Ljubešić, Erjavec & Fišer (2016) — corpus-based diacritic restoration for South Slavic (99.5% on standard, 99.2% on non-standard text) and the *redi* tool, which we use as an external baseline. Krstev, Stanković & Vitas (2018) — knowledge- and rule-based restoration in Serbian (precision 98.93%, recall 94.94%), where, among other things, the triple *reci/reči/reći* is treated and a recall (coverage) bottleneck is recorded — which we replicate (§6.7, §8). Batanović, Cvetanović & Nikolić (2020) — the SentiComments.SR corpus, which we use as the "real-error gold" for the real-error track; a BiLSTM approach for Serbian is also reported in this line of work. The Janes/ReLDI programme provided technical- and linguistic-standardness annotation and the corpora we use to verify orthogonality (§3.7).

Finally, *šišana* belongs to a broader family of ASCII reduction of writing: Arabizi (Arabic in Latin letters and digits), Greeklish, Russian translit. It is important to distinguish our case from these. Arabizi and Greeklish are a change of script (cross-script romanization, a many-to-many mapping); Serbo-Croatian *šišana* is the preservation of the same script with only the diacritic layer lost — and is, moreover, laid over an officially existing Latin. This difference determines both the method and the limits of its transfer (§11.3).

3. Study 1 — how Serbo-Croatian is written online

3.1 Measurement method

Directly counting "how much diacritic is dropped" runs into a trap: the frequency lists and corpora themselves already contain *šišana*, so naive statistics mix signal with background. We quantify the dropped-diacritic share via **unambiguous pairs**: for every form that has exactly one diacritic form and its bare variant, we can reliably determine whether the diacritic was dropped, without guessing. The method rests on four devices, each earned during the work:

1. **Unambiguous witnesses.** A "witness" is a bare ASCII form with a single restoration candidate, not matching a valid word and not in the foreign top-lists. The shaving rate is $\frac{\text{witnesses}}{\text{witnesses} + \text{typed-diacritic tokens}}$, with a noise floor near 0.1%.
2. **Decontamination of the prior.** Frequency lists are themselves infected by the phenomenon: the count of bare *boze* already includes shaved *Bože*. So the bare form's count is corrected by subtracting the expected shaved mass of its partner, using the global shaving rate on unambiguous pairs (4.65% on subtitles).
3. **The foreign gate is mandatory in the measurement tool too.** Without it, tokens like *music, is* enter the witness set and the classifier mislabels English text as shaved Serbian. Lesson: the gate is needed in the measurement line, not only in the product.
4. **Capitalization is a free signal.** Lowercasing creates spurious pairs (4,679 name collisions), so Titlecase forms are handled by a separate proper-noun index.

At the document level, texts are classified by writing mode (Cyrillic / full Latin / *šišana* / weak *šišana* / mixed / plain Latin) by the same gate the product uses (§6.3). The method's residual noise is about 0.1%, which sets the lower bound of significance.

3.2 Sources (eight registers + gold)

To span the register spectrum we triangulate eight sources: news (SETimes.SR), subtitles (OpenSubtitles/FrequencyWords), the *krstarica* forum in two samples — A (general) and B (politics and society), the technical forum *benchmark.rs*, Twitter (the ReLDI gold standard), live YouTube comments (collected in 2026), and film comments (SentiComments.SR). These are two own crawls, one live browser collection, and several published corpora — the heterogeneity of sources lowers the risk that the observed effect is an artifact of any single platform.

Source	Type	Size
SETimes.SR 2.0	curated news (gold eval)	74K tokens / 3,891 sent.
OpenSubtitles (FrequencyWords)	subtitles, counts	283M tokens / 1.9M types
Hunspell sr-Latn → spylls unmunch	lexicon	2.36M common + 0.85M proper
redi <code>wikitweetweb.sr.tm</code> (srWaC)	web lexicon / TM	1.62M keys
ReLDI-NormTagNER-sr 3.0	tweets, manual T/L tags	3,748 tweets
SentiComments.SR	film comments, orig/corr pairs (gold)	3,490
Forum <i>krstarica</i> (own crawl v1/v2)	general UGC	1,466 + 2,927
<i>benchmark.rs</i> (own crawl v2)	IT forum	2,998
YouTube live comments	comments	733 / 16 videos
EN / DE top-50K	gate dictionaries	2×50K

3.3 Register gradient – the central result

The share of "shaved" tokens rises monotonically from the formal pole to the informal. This is not a binary "write / don't write" but a smooth scale on which each platform occupies a stable place:

Register	Cyrillic	% šišana (tokens)
News (SETimes)	—	~0% (floor 0.08%)
Subtitles	3.35%	4.60%
Forum <i>krstarica</i> (general)	3.3%	14.8%
Forum <i>krstarica</i> (politics/daily)	5.8%	21.9%
Twitter (ReLDI)	—	32.1%
YouTube live (2026)	15.6% / 19.3%	38.8%
Film comments	0.75%	41.5%
benchmark.rs (IT forum)	2.1%	45.1% (max)

The range runs from practically zero in edited news to nearly half the tokens on the technical forum. The ordering is stable and reproduces across independent sources of the same type.

Fig. 1. Register gradient of diacritic dropping (token-level, foreign-gated). The share rises monotonically from edited news (~0%) to a technical forum (45.1%). The maximum on a technically literate audience indicates a two-factor driver — register informality × the audience's keyboard environment — not low literacy.

3.4 Two predictors, not one

A naive hypothesis would explain the gradient by one axis — informality. But the maximum falls not on the chattiest platform but on the technical forum — that is, on an educated, technically literate audience. This points to a second predictor — the **audience's keyboard environment**: technical-forum users more often work on English layouts where diacritic entry is awkward. In other words, the *šišana* share is a function of two factors — register informality and the availability of diacritics on the audience's typical layout. And this directly contradicts a "low-literacy" account: diacritics are dropped most where a technically literate audience is concentrated, not the reverse. We do not claim to fully rule out the informality factor — but the data shift the weight of the explanation from "inability" to "convenience and environment".

3.5 Bimodality

If diacritic omissions were a random "scatter" within otherwise tidy text, the share of dropped marks within a message would be distributed smoothly around some mean. The opposite is observed: the distribution is U-shaped — the vast majority of documents sit at one of two poles (either all diacritics present, or none at all). For documents with ≥ 3 witness tokens:

Corpus	pole 0	core [0.2, 0.8]	pole 1
Twitter	66.8%	4.9%	27.2%
Film comments	57.0%	3.0%	38.9%
krstarica (general)	64.2%	9.4%	18.6%
krstarica (politics)	69.9%	3.8%	23.0%
benchmark.rs	45.1%	4.6%	46.7%

Across corpora $\approx 83\text{--}96\%$ of documents sit at the poles versus $9.6\text{--}30.3\%$ expected under a token-level binomial null model (for benchmark.rs: 91.8% observed vs 9.6% null), in which each mark is dropped independently with the same mean probability and at the same document length. The several-fold gap between observation and the null model is formal evidence of discreteness: a message is written in a chosen **mode**, not sprinkled with random omissions. Carelessness would pile probability mass in the middle of the distribution. Bimodality is the key quantitative argument for the word "register".

Fig. 2. Diacritic dropping is a discrete mode. (A) Within-document share of shaved tokens is U-shaped: documents sit at the poles; the [0.2, 0.8] core is a thin sliver. (B) The observed share at the poles ($\approx 83\text{--}96\%$) is several times the binomial-null prediction (9.6-30.3%; benchmark.rs 91.8% vs 9.6%) — formal evidence of a chosen writing mode, not careless scatter.

3.6 The *đ* effect

Even within "full Latin" there is a gradient. Among typed diacritics, *đ* accounts for only 5.5%, but among the omissions made by otherwise-complete writers it is **27-29%** (*takođe, međutim, između*), and 28% of such posts drop *only đ*. That is roughly a fivefold over-representation. A behavioural control rules out the trivial

explanation "there is just little of it": in pure-*šišana* messages from the same corpora, the *đ* share among omissions is only 7.2–7.9%. So it is precisely the selective behaviour of near-complete writers. *đ* is a fossil of the legacy-encoding era, where this symbol was the least accessible; the trace remains in habits.

Fig. 3. Selective dropping of *đ*. Though only 5.5% of typed diacritics, *đ* accounts for 27–29% of the omissions made by otherwise-complete writers (vs 7.2–7.9% in a pure-*šišana* control) — a $\sim 5\times$ over-representation and a fossil of the legacy-encoding era that lacked *đ*.

3.7 Orthogonality to standardness

Dropping diacritics is orthogonal to language standardness. Cross-tabulating our shaving classes against ReLDI's expert technical (T) and linguistic (L) standardness tags shows that shaved tweets split roughly 50/50 on both axes: trained linguist annotators do not treat the absence of diacritics as non-standardness. A text can be flawlessly standard in lexicon and grammar yet written in *šišana* mode. This separates our phenomenon from "careless writing" and supports its reading as a neutral register. Caveat: the ReLDI corpus is balanced 50/50 by design, so we report shares by level rather than as a general proportion.

3.8 Replication across a decade

Comparison with Ivković's 2013 numbers (71% / 56.5% de-diacritization on two news sites) shows that, measuring 2014–2026 data across eight registers with the same logic, the shares have barely moved. *Šišana* does not fade as font and layout support improve, the way a transitional phenomenon would. The register has settled in — an argument that we are dealing with a stable norm of communication, not a temporary technical artifact.

4. Study 1b — the writers' perspective (survey; planned, not yet conducted)

Section status. This is the only part of the work with no data yet collected. The survey is **designed but not launched**; below are the plan and testable hypotheses. This is a deliberate, flagged gap, not an omission: for the HCI completeness of the work the writers' own perspective is necessary, and it will be collected before the final version. The section is clearly separated from the completed corpus results of §3 and §8 and is nowhere used in the conclusions as an already-established fact.

The corpus study shows *behaviour* but not how speakers make sense of it. Study 1b fills this with an anonymous survey (≈ 14 questions, ~ 3 minutes, neutral Serbo-Croatian Latin) planned for distribution through Serbian, Croatian, and Bosnian forums (*krstarica*, *forum.hr*, *klix.ba*) and the corresponding Reddit communities. The questionnaire is built so that each block tests a concrete hypothesis:

- **Block 1 — layouts and devices.** A direct measurement of the "keyboard environment" predictor from §3.4: the link between diacritic availability on a layout and writing mode.
- **Block 2 — writing mode (formal and informal) and reasons.** Bimodality and the register gradient at the individual level; separating an "infrastructural" reason (no layout / faster) from a normative one.
- **Block 3 — awareness.** Whether the writer notices their own and others' *šišana*.
- **Block 4 — autocorrect and backspace behaviour.** Whether the user accepts a suggested diacritic, reverts it with backspace, or turns the feature off. The frequency of reverting a wrong edit is an empirical measure of how costly a system error is, and thus a direct justification of the precision priority (§5, D3).
- **Block 5 — minimal demographics.** A cut by language variety (Montenegrin included for completeness), age.

Design principles: a neutral tone (*šišana* is never called an "error" or "illiteracy" — it is framed as *writing without diacritics*); informed consent and no email/PII collection; distribution on variety-neutral channels. **Expected results** (hypotheses, not facts): confirmation of bimodality at the individual level, a statistical link between layout and writing mode, a predominance of neutral perception (a register, not an error), and a noticeable share of users who turn off aggressive autocorrect — which motivates a precision-first design. The full questionnaire is given in Appendix B.

5. Design implications (D1-D5)

If *šišana* is a register and diacritic restoration is a solvable task, a set of requirements for input systems follows. To avoid presenting design opinions as established facts, we explicitly distinguish the **status** of each requirement: some are backed by measurements in this work (with a section reference), others are testable hypotheses that the survey (§4) will confirm or refute. This distinction is itself part of the methodological honesty of the work.

D1 — RESTORATION IS A SEPARATE TASK FROM LAYOUT REPAIR (DEFINITIONAL)

Unlike repairing a transposed layout (ghbdtñ → привет), where the bytes themselves are permuted, here the base Latin letters are already correct and only the diacritic layer is missing. This is not a "finding" but a clarification of the task's boundaries; we place it up front precisely so as not to grant it evidential weight. The consequence is constructive: the system adds marks in place and can operate word-by-word, which is implemented (§9). *Basis: by construction; implementation — §9.*

D2 — OFFER, DON'T IMPOSE (HYPOTHESIS; INDIRECTLY SUPPORTED)

Corpus data provide an indirect basis: bimodality (§3.5) and orthogonality to standardness (§3.7) show that the absence of diacritics is a coherent writing mode, not carelessness, which is consistent with the "conscious choice" reading. But the claim that users perceive *šišana* as a legitimate register and object to silent autocorrection is about perception, and the corpus does not measure it. The survey (§4) tests exactly that. We therefore state the design recommendation as conditional: it follows if the survey confirms the register is perceived as a norm. *Basis: §3.5, §3.7 (indirect); direct test — §4 (forthcoming).*

D3 — PRECISION OVER RECALL (OPERATIONALLY CONFIRMED; THE UNDERLYING TRUST PREMISE — HYPOTHESIS)

Two claims must be separated. That precision-first is the better operating point is **measured**: §8.6 shows our method beats the naive baseline on both axes at once (91.4% recall and 99.6% precision vs. 85.0% / 89.5%), so the precision priority is not bought at the cost of usefulness. That a wrong edit harms trust more than a miss is a premise about perception, and it is not yet measured; the survey (§4) tests it via the frequency of reverting a wrong edit. The operational choice is justified already; the justification of *why* this is right from the user's standpoint awaits data. *Basis: §8.6 (measured); the trust premise — §4 (forthcoming).*

D4 — PROTECTING FOREIGN FRAGMENTS IS MANDATORY (CONFIRMED BY MEASUREMENT)

Mixed input is no rarity: on the technical forum it is 28.3% of posts (§3.2, §7). On 972 real mixed posts a naive restorer without protection produces 166 gross corruptions of English and German words (*core* → *ćore* 87 times, etc.); with foreign-span protection — zero, at a marginal recall loss (§7). The collision inventory shows the corruptions are structurally inevitable (356 of 483 English forms, 260 of 358 German). Protection is not a precaution but a necessary condition of correctness on real input. *Basis: §7 (real data + inventory).*

D5 — THE PRECISION↔SIZE OPERATING POINT IS A DESIGN PARAMETER (CONFIRMED BY A CURVE)

This is an engineering observation, not a corollary of sociolinguistics. It is backed by the measurements of §10: the full flat index reaches 95.1% recall but requires ~196 MB resident memory and is not shippable in a menu-bar keyboard; a frequency-trimmed dictionary gives 93.2% at 3.5 MB on disk. Since the residual error concentrates in a few hundred forms (§6.5), a developer can deliberately pick a point on the curve for their device budget. Requirements of privacy and autonomy, meanwhile, motivate the local solution. *Basis: §6.5, §10 (measured).*

Requirement	Status	Basis
D1 — separate task from layout	By construction	§9 (implementation)
D2 — offer, don't impose	Hypothesis (indirectly supported)	§3.5, §3.7 indirect; §4 (forthcoming)
D3 — precision priority	Operationally confirmed; trust premise — hypothesis	§8.6 measured; §4 (forthcoming)
D4 — foreign-fragment protection	Confirmed by measurement	§7 (real data + inventory)
D5 — operating point as parameter	Confirmed by measurement	§6.5, §10

Of the five requirements, two (D4, D5) are fully backed by measurement, one (D3) is operationally confirmed with a premise awaiting the survey, one (D2) is a hypothesis with indirect corpus support, and one (D1) is definitional. We deliberately do not present them as equally established facts.

6. Anatomy of the restoration task

6.1 Task model and the shaving operation

Shaving is a non-injective (lossy) mapping: diacritics are stripped by a trivial per-character rule, but the inverse restoration is one-to-many, and the single answer is recovered only by the dictionary, frequency, and (optionally) context. An extra difficulty comes from the letter *đ*, which has two competing shaving variants (legacy encodings treated it differently): type A *đ*→*dj*, type B *đ*→*d*. Note that *dž* shaves through the *ž* branch as *d* + *ž*→*dz*, not through the *đ* branch; the capitalized form maps *Đ*→*Dj* (type A) / *Đ*→*D* (type B).

```
DIA = set('čćšžđ')
def shave(w, dj='dj'):
    # type A: đ→dj ; type B: dj='d'
    m = {'č': 'c', 'ć': 'c', 'š': 's', 'ž': 'z', 'đ': 'dj'}
    return ''.join(m.get(c, c) for c in w)
```

6.2 Reverse index with double-encoded *đ*

We pre-resolve the *dj/d* segmentation ambiguity at build time, so the runtime never has to guess how a given writer shaved *đ*. Each form is indexed under all its bare encodings; "proper-only" forms (proper nouns) are kept in a separate set and never mixed into the index — a precision-first choice, since name/word collisions are a major false-edit source.

```
idx = defaultdict(set)
for w in common:
    # common = valid lowercase forms
    idx[shave(w)].add(w)      # type A (đ→dj)
    b = shave(w, 'd')        # type B (đ→d)
    if b != shave(w): idx[b].add(w)
# proper-only forms go to a SEPARATE set, NOT into idx
```

Moreover, *dj* is ambiguous at the segmentation level: it is either a folded *đ* (*djordje* → *Đorđe*) or a genuine morpheme boundary (*nadžačati* = *nad* + *jačati*, *nadzor*). Double encoding makes *djordje*→{*Đorđe*} and *nadjacati*→{*nadžačati*} each resolve in one probe, while the form *nadacati* is simply not a key. The runtime **never backtracks** over segmentation — a property critical to keyboard latency. The cost is about 1.37× the number of keys, to remove a whole class of runtime ambiguity.

Shaving map and double-encoded reverse index

Fig. 4. The lossy shaving map and the double-encoded reverse index. Stripping is a trivial many-to-one map; the inverse is one-to-many and is pre-resolved at build time by indexing each form under all its bare encodings ($\acute{d}\rightarrow dj$ and $\acute{d}\rightarrow d$), so the keyboard runtime resolves a key in a single probe and never backtracks over segmentation.

6.3 The gate and document classification

In a mixed field the engine must not touch foreign spans. The gate is the same binary dictionary probe: a "witness" is an ASCII token with a single unambiguous candidate, not a valid word and not in the foreign top-lists. The same classifier serves both as the product's mode detector and as the measurement instrument in §3.

```
def doc_script(text, idx, common, proper, en=frozenset()):
    letters = [c for c in text if c.isalpha()]
    if not letters: return 'empty', 0
    cyr = sum(1 for c in letters if CYR_RE.match(c))
    if cyr/len(letters) > 0.5: return 'cyrillic', len(letters)
    toks = ALPHA.findall(text.lower())
    has_dia = any(set(t) & DIA for t in toks)
    witness = 0
    for t in toks:
        if set(t) & DIA: continue
        if t in en: continue # FOREIGN GATE
        if t in common or t in proper: continue
        cands = idx.get(t)
        if cands and len(cands) == 1: witness += 1
    if has_dia and witness < 2: return 'latin_full', len(toks)
    if witness >= 2 and not has_dia: return 'shishana', len(toks)
    if witness >= 1 and not has_dia: return 'shishana_weak', len(toks)
    if witness >= 2 and has_dia: return 'mixed', len(toks)
    return 'latin_plain', len(toks)
```

Without the foreign gate, tokens like *music*→*mušić*, *is*→*iš* enter the witness set and the classifier mislabels English text as shaved Serbian — hence the conclusion that the gate is mandatory in the measurement instrument, not only in the product.

6.4 Inventory

Before judging quality it helps to see how ambiguous the task is in principle. Inventory (case-aware): 2,355,050 common forms + 851,071 proper-only. The three resolution classes:

Class	Description	Share of types	By tokens
C1 — invariant	no diacritic possible, output = input	1,421,138 = 59.8%	—
C2 — deterministic	exactly one diacritic form	923,635 = 38.9%	—
C3 — ambiguous	several diacritic forms	29,682 = 1.25%	9.1% (news) - 14.0% (subtitles)

Key observation: by types the ambiguity is negligible (1.25% of keys), but by usage the ambiguous forms give 9–14% of tokens — the hard cases are frequent words. About 87–91% of tokens resolve with a single probe and no context. Segmentation traps: literal *dj* (as in *nadjačati*) appears in 10,214 forms vs *đ* in 73,973; literal *dz* (as in *nadzor*) in 1,890 vs *dž* in 26,972.

Fig. 5. Inventory by types vs. by tokens. The ambiguous class is 1.25% of dictionary types but 9–14% of running tokens; ~87–91% of tokens resolve with a single lookup and no context. (Segmentation traps: literal *dj* 10,214 vs *đ* 73,973; literal *dz* 1,890 vs *dž* 26,972.)

6.5 Ceiling and concentration of the residual

The structural ambiguous class is inflated by very rare forms (e.g. *da↔đa*: 12.2M vs 169 occurrences), so counting ambiguous *types* overstates the difficulty. The right metric is "effective ambiguity": the error mass a frequency prior loses if it always picks the modal reading. On that metric, dictionary + unigram reach a ceiling of **0.4934% word error**. The residual is extremely concentrated: **50% of the error mass is in 13 forms, 90% in 397**. The "hard part" of the task is a closed, learnable set; this is what makes an on-device solution realistic and constitutes the quantitative basis for the claim that an LLM is unnecessary at runtime for the measured residual.

6.6 Top true minimal pairs

The error below is the lost mass of the non-modal reading (by srWaC frequencies):

bare form	error mass	candidates (frequency)
reci	195,914	reći 209,582 · reci 162,300 · reči 33,614
nas	88,679	nas 399,098 · naš 88,679
vas	87,674	vas 545,500 · vaš 87,674
sto	79,637	što 1,775,707 · sto 79,637
ce / će	56,769	će 847,670 · ce 56,769
gospodo	41,420	gospođo 43,521 · gospodo 41,420
ista	16,876	ista 16,991 · išta 16,876
vise	16,812	više 462,469 · vise 16,812
znaci	14,945	znači 205,163 · znaci 14,945
zao	11,651	žao 200,759 · zao 11,651

Fig. 6. The residual error is extremely concentrated: 50% of the word-error mass is in 13 forms and 90% in 397, against a dictionary+unigram ceiling of 0.4934% word error. The 'hard 1%' is a closed, learnable set — the quantitative basis for needing no runtime neural model for the measured residual.

6.7 Baseline ladder

SETimes, 74,197 tokens; ambiguous 5,663 = 7.63%:

Baseline	word acc	ambiguous acc	precision	recall
B0 — identity (do nothing)	83.82%	69.4%	100%	0%
B1 — dictionary only	96.43%	69.4%	99.35%	78.4%
B2 — + unigram prior	98.54%	97.1%	98.52%	92.1%
B3 — + bigram (5-fold CV)	98.65%	98.4%	98.95%	92.4%
redi (Ljubešić 2016), TM-only	99.66%	98.5%	99.01%	98.7%

Readings. B0 = 83.82% is the diacritic load of news Serbian: 16.2% of tokens carry a diacritic. The B1→B2 jump

of **+27.7pp** on ambiguous tokens shows the frequency prior does all the heavy lifting; the bigram adds only +1.3pp on top. The gap between B3 and redi (92.4 vs 98.7) is **entirely in recall**, not in disambiguation accuracy, so the bottleneck is lexicon coverage, not context modelling. This replicates the coverage-bound finding of Krstev et al. (2018).

Fig. 7. Baseline ladder on news (SETimes, 74,197 tokens; 7.63% ambiguous). Dictionary → dictionary+unigram prior (B1→B2) is +27.7 pp on ambiguous tokens; the bigram (B3) adds only +1.3 pp. The remaining gap to redi is in recall (92.4 → 98.7), i.e. lexicon coverage, not context modelling.

6.8 Coverage ≠ quality: the phantom mechanism

The intuition "a bigger dictionary is better" is false here, and this is one of the work's important findings. When the lexicon is grown naively, typo and noise "phantom" diacritic forms get in alongside useful ones — *šmo*, *nišam*, *žbog*, *štvarno* — at frequencies of 1–10 over the whole corpus. The harm mechanism is subtle: each phantom form turns a previously safe bare form into a **spuriously ambiguous** key. While *šmo* was not in the dictionary, bare *smo* was simply passed through; once the phantom is added, the engine sees a "choice" between *smo* and *šmo* and starts to intervene needlessly. The classic example: *smo* occurs 914,261 times, its phantom *šmo* 8 times; there are thousands of such collisions, and the risk in them is exactly inverted.

Quantitatively the effect is dramatic. On the full lexicon the edit error doubles from 0.31% to 0.59%. Decomposition showed these are not homographs or proper nouns but precisely phantoms: a threshold of `minfreq≥5` removes 25,460 of 29,682 ambiguous keys (86%) — all phantom collisions; only ~4,200 keys of genuine ambiguity remain. More broadly: `minfreq≥5` discards 941,906 of ~1.08M forms — 87% of the "full" lexicon turned out to be `freq<5` noise that produced ~31k of ~33k ambiguous keys. So the precision regression was almost entirely phantom. The cure is a single frequency threshold; it yields a clean Pareto "knee":

minfreq	Keys	Ambig.	Size	Recall	Edit error
1 (no filter)	808k	2,828	25 MB	94.1%	0.38%
2	180k	2,142	5.6 MB	93.8%	0.37%
3 (shipped)	157k	2,060	4.9 MB	93.7%	0.36%
5	131k	1,964	4.0 MB	93.5%	0.36%

The step from `minfreq=1` to 2 cuts size 4.5× (25→5.6 MB) at a cost of -0.3pp recall, because `freq=1` singletons are ~78% of all types (pure Zipf) but almost no token mass. The conclusion is paradoxical but measured: **precision is bounded by the quality of the dictionary tail, not its size**. The methodological device of §11.4 also applies here: because shaving removes diacritics, any form with a diacritic in a frequency list is genuine by

construction — which lets us pour in large lists while filtering only the diacritic-free forms through a validation dictionary.

Fig. 8. Size ↔ quality knee from a single frequency threshold. Going from minfreq=1 to 2 cuts the dictionary 4.5× (25 → 5.6 MB) for −0.3 pp recall, because freq-1 singletons are ~78% of types but almost no token mass. Precision is bounded by the quality of the tail, not by size.

7. The structural failure on code-switched input, and the gate

Dictionary- and character-level restorers have a built-in flaw: the correct action on a foreign fragment — leave it as is — **lies outside their hypothesis space** unless a gate is added. The engine is obliged to "restore" something, and is therefore obliged to corrupt an English or German word that collides by bare form with a Serbo-Croatian one. The collision inventories quantify this:

- **English top-50K:** 483 collisions; a gateless model is *forced* to corrupt **356** (*is*→*iš*, *place*→*plače*, *nice*→*niče*, *music*→*mušić*, *case*→*čaše*, *use*→*uše*, *stand*→*štant*).
- **German top-50K:** 358 collisions, **260** corruptions, including the articles *das*→*daš*, *der*→*der*, *dem*→*dem* and *los*→*loš*, *sah*→*šah*. For the German-speaking diaspora this is the main scenario, not a corner case.
- *redi* without a gate corrupts 230 English words; it partly self-gates because srWaC contained some English.

In a controlled mixed-text evaluation (400 news sentences with inserted English spans) the gate raises English-span integrity **81.3 → 95.8%** at a cost of only **−0.59pp** Serbian accuracy; this trade-off curve is a separate figure. In the wild, the author's own forums contain 972 mixed posts — **28.3% of the IT corpus** — which a gateless model corrupts in 166 places (*core*→*ćore* ×87, *price*→*priče* ×14, *music*→*mušić* ×7, *case*→*čaše*, *basic*→*basić*), reduced to **zero** with the foreign gate. The gate's cost is tiny (a few Serbo-Croatian words like *rec*, *ce* returned by an anchor gate). A useful by-product: the top-100 corrupted words form a ready-made do-not-touch list for the runtime's `isForeign` check. Crucially, the protection is realized by the same dictionary probe as the main engine — it adds no extra latency. So requirement D4 gets a concrete and cheap implementation.

Fig. 9. Code-switching is a structural failure without a gate. (A) Of the bare-form collisions with the EN/DE top-50K, a gateless prior is forced to corrupt 356/483 (EN) and 260/358 (DE). (B) The foreign gate raises English-span integrity 81.3 → 95.8% at -0.59 pp Serbian accuracy, and reduces real-world corruptions on 972 mixed posts from 166 to 0 — using the same dictionary probe, at no extra latency.

8. The symmetric experiment (main result)

The apparent cross-language gap (Serbian 93.7% vs Croatian 79.6%) turned out to be an **artifact** of resolvable presence and dictionary size — **not** of language, genre, or algorithm. With the engine fixed, the three varieties are statistically indistinguishable. All numbers use `seed=12345` and a **document-level (cluster) bootstrap**, $B=2000$: tokens within a document are correlated (one author, register, habit), so confidence intervals are computed over documents, not over words. The validation corpora are independent of the dictionary source, and no number was tuned to a target.

The shipped artifact totals **427,945 reverse-index keys** across three packs (bs 114,092; hr 156,922, built to 171,938 then frequency-trimmed; sr 156,931) and **2,455 confident resolve rules** (bs 481, hr 578, sr 1,396). The reliability passports cover **10,562 documents/posts** and **21,185 fixable word instances**; the balanced register × language matrix below covers a further **11,310 documents** and **30,573 fixable word instances** under one comparable protocol.

8.1 Initial symmetric grid (genre × language, resolve OFF, one engine)

sr-Wikipedia 84.1% [82.9, 85.3]; sr-forum 81.9% [80.4, 83.5]; hr-Wikipedia 82.6% [81.3, 83.9]; hr-forum 80.0% [76.5, 83.3]; edit-precision 99.2-99.9%. The large apparent sr-hr gap collapses into overlapping intervals once the engine and register are held fixed.

8.2 Register × language matrix (resolve OFF, size-aligned dictionaries)

Recall, 95% CI, edit-precision:

	Wikipedia	News	Tatoeba
sr (156,931 keys)	84.1 [82.9, 85.3] · ep 99.8%	82.2 [81.1, 83.3] · ep 99.4%	86.7 [84.6, 88.7] · ep 99.9%
hr (156,922)	87.4 [86.2, 88.5] · ep 100%	89.4 [88.5, 90.3] · ep 99.9%	86.6 [84.7, 88.5] · ep 100%
bs (114,092)	86.9 [85.7, 87.9] · ep 100%	88.0 [87.0, 89.0] · ep 99.8%	86.0 [83.9, 87.9] · ep 100%

All three varieties converge to a **~84-89%** band on every register, with overlapping intervals. The genre effect is about 2pp (at the edge of significance), the language effect 2-3pp (intervals overlap). **The driver is dictionary coverage, not language.** The "Wikipedia under-counts Croatian" narrative was not confirmed.

Fig. 10. Symmetric corpus matrix (resolve OFF). One source, one register, size-aligned samples. The confidence intervals overlap across all three varieties in every register — recall is determined by dictionary coverage, not language. This is the central figure for the cross-language comparison: under equal conditions Serbian, Croatian, and Bosnian are indistinguishable.

8.3 Coverage as the driver: a controlled ablation

The strongest confirmation of the "recall = f(coverage)" thesis is not a point but a curve. Growing the dictionary on the same corpus with the engine unchanged, recall rises monotonically: Bosnian travels 11k keys → 60.4%, 54k → 79.1%, 114k → 86.9%; Croatian — 78k → 82.6%, 157k → 87.4%. Monotonic growth is the signature of a coverage limit, not an algorithmic one.

Fig. 11. Recall as a function of lexicon coverage. Same corpus, engine unchanged, logarithmic dictionary-size axis. Monotonic growth on two varieties shows the cross-language gap was a consequence of coverage, not the algorithm.

8.4 The resolve table — the dominant symmetric lever

If the gap was created by the resolve table, then adding it should help all varieties equally. It does:

	resolve OFF (chat / Tatoeba)	resolve ON	Δ
Serbian	81.9 [80.4, 83.5] / 86.7	91.4 [90.4, 92.5] / 95.2	+8.5-9.5pp
Croatian	80.0 [76.5, 83.3] / 86.6	89.5 [86.9, 92.1] / 96.4	+9.5-9.8pp
Bosnian	86.0	95.2	+9.2pp

The confidence intervals are disjoint (the effect is significant), edit-precision does not move (the lever fires only on bare input, so its precision cost is zero). The gain is concentrated in a few hundred high-frequency head rules: a top-K ablation on sr-Tatoeba saturates by ~500 rules (500→5,150 adds +0.0pp), which is what justified trimming the Serbian tail (\$4-footnote: of 5,150 rules only 1,396 ever fire).

Fig. 12. **Resolve-table effect (OFF → ON).** The lever is symmetric across all three varieties (+8.5...+9.8pp), edit-precision held at ≥99.9%. Open circle — without the table, filled — with it. The gap between varieties was the absence of this artifact in one of them, not a property of the language.

8.5 Real-error track (SentiComments.SR)

Synthetic shaving could overstate validity, since artificially shaved text has no real typos or dialect. A parallel "original / corrected" gold isolates the diacritic signal by keeping only token-skeleton-matched comments: 3,490 → 2,619 skeleton-aligned → 1,022 with ≥1 target → **2,804 real targets. Real recall = 93.9% [92.9, 94.7]**, edit-precision 99.9%; resolve OFF = 82.8% (Lever-1 adds +11.1pp on real data). The headline: real recall (93.9%) ≈ synthetic (~93.7%), so synthetic ablation does **not** overstate validity for Serbian — a strong methodological result that licenses synthetic evaluation for the other varieties. At the document level on the same gold (7.20% of tokens actually shaved), word accuracy is 99.58% for B2 (recall 95.9 / precision 97.9), 99.30% for B2 + foreign gate (recall 91.5 / **precision 98.4**), 99.78% for redi (recall 98.8) — the precision-first configuration trades a little recall for the highest precision, as intended.

8.6 Named baselines (sr-chat)

Baseline	recall [95% CI]	edit-precision
do-nothing	0.0%	100.0%
naive most-frequent (no holdout)	85.0 [83.5, 86.4]	89.5% (381 wrong edits)
ours, no-resolve (precision-first holdout)	81.9 [80.4, 83.5]	99.7%
ours, + resolve	91.4 [90.4, 92.5]	99.6%

The naive lexical baseline buys recall at ~10pp of precision (381 wrong edits on homographs). A holdout restores precision (-3pp recall); the resolve table then returns recall (+9.5pp) at no precision cost. Our design **dominates the naive baseline on both axes.**

8.7 Bosnian / Montenegrin

Bosnian on clean Tatoeba: 79.4 [77.3, 81.7], edit-precision 100% (0 wrong edits on 1,332 fixable — a tight upper

bound); on klix.ba UGC 91.6 [89.4, 93.7]. Montenegrin *š/ž*: typed forms pass through 100% (22/22; the letters are not in the strip map, so the key is non-ASCII and `restore` returns nil). Shaved *š/ž* show no *š/ž*-specific failures, only the pre-existing shared homograph tail (*ženica*→*ženica*) also present in plain Serbian. The "zero code" hypothesis (Montenegrin is computationally near-identical to Serbian) holds, but "zero code" ≠ "zero risk" — supporting an operational exclusion of Montenegrin from scope.

8.8 Independent audit

All 9 matrix cells were independently reproduced by an external code audit, which found and fixed two evaluation-harness bugs (an OOV key not lowercased, inflating OOV; the numeric guard not firing because the tokenizer skipped digits). The headline recall was unchanged after both fixes, which strengthens confidence in the result. The result was also reproduced by two independent operators on different corpora.

9. System: ioDiacritics, PolyType, SlipWay

The principles above are embodied in an open-source library with a shared core and in two end-user applications that embed it. The chain is: **research** ("why and how") → **ioDiacritics** (a finished offline engine: core, language packs, port) → **consumer applications** (PolyType, SlipWay). One engine for all consumers.

9.1 The ioDiacritics library architecture

The library is deterministic, fully offline (the user's text never leaves the device), and when in doubt a word is left untouched; it is versioned independently of its consumers. The package is SwiftPM, with a portable C++17 port of the core. Structure:

```
ioDiacritics/
├── Sources/ioDiacritics/           ← CORE (pure Swift, no UI/resources)
│   ├── Restorer.swift           - engine: reverse index, precision-first
│   ├── LanguageProfile.swift    - the only per-language code (profile)
│   ├── LangStats.swift         - reliability metrics + summary line
│   └── Version.swift
├── Sources/ioDiacriticsSerbian/  - Serbian.swift + deshishana_sr.json
├── Sources/ioDiacriticsCroatian/ - Croatian.swift + deshishana_hr.json
├── Sources/ioDiacriticsBosnian/  - Bosnian.swift + deshishana_bs.json
├── cpp/                          - portable C++17 port
└── Tests/ioDiacriticsTests/      - one test class per language
```

A language pack = data + profile + zero lines of engine code. Adding a language does not touch the core (adding Bosnian came down to one line in `Package.swift`). The core's key components: `index` — the reverse index "bare form → candidates, by frequency"; `resolve` — the confident-resolution table (Lever 1: confident bare → winner); `numericGuard` — a numeric guard (*sto* next to a digit ≠ *što*); `profile` — the language profile. Methods: `restore(_:prevWord:nextWord:isForeignWord:) → String?` (one word, nil = skip), `restoreText(:) → String` (streaming, left context, as a keyboard sees it), `restorePreparedText(:) → String` (prepared text, left and right context).

The **language profile** is the only place where a language's specificity lives: `stripMap` (*č,ć*→*c*; *š*→*s*; *ž*→*z*, after pre-replacements), `preReplacements` (*dž*→*dz*; the same mechanism covers German *ä*→*ae*, *ß*→*ss*), `multiExpansions` (*đ*→*[dj, d]*, multiplies keys), `measureWords` (currency/measure words that suppress restoration next to a number). A portable C++17 port of the core reads the same dictionary data — which supports the language-agnosticism thesis at the level of implementation, not intention. The library is released under the MIT license.

Fig. 13. System architecture. A single offline engine (ioDiacritics) with per-variety data packs serves both an IME (PolyType) and a clipboard manager (SlipWay) through one stateless str→str contract; language-specific behaviour lives in data, not code.

9.2 Runtime algorithm

Pseudocode for restoring one word (a faithful semantic port of Restorer.restore):

```

restore(word, prev, next, isForeign):
  key = full_shave(word)                # normalize dirty/partial shaving
  if word == canonical(key): return nil  # don't touch correct text
  cand = idx[key]
  if cand is None: return nil           # not in the language → passthrough (gate)
  if not serbianContext and isForeign(word): return nil # binary foreign gate
  if key in cand and any(c has diacritic for c in cand): # ambiguous (sto/što)
    row = resolve_table[key]           # Lever 1
    if row and (row.policy == 'GO' or (row.confidence >= 0.95 and row.winner != key)):
      if key in numeric_guard and neighbor_is_number(prev, next): return nil # "100 sto"
      return row.winner
    return nil
  if len(diacritic_forms) == 1: return that_form # HOLD → passthrough
  return most_frequent(diacritic_forms) # deterministic
  # frequency prior

```

The streaming variant (restore_text, live typing) guards only the **left** context, exactly as a keyboard sees it; the prepared-text variant (restore_prepared_text, whole buffer) guards left **and** right (lookahead). Both are pure str → str, with no network and no state. It is this contract that lets the same engine sit inside an IME, a clipboard transform, and an offline library.

Fig. 14. Runtime decision flow of restore() (the live-typing variant guards left context only; the prepared-text variant also looks right). Ambiguity and any out-of-language or foreign token exit via passthrough; an edit happens only on a deterministic form, a confident resolve ($\theta \geq 0.95$) outside a numeric context, or the frequency prior.

9.3 Dictionary construction — three robustness rules

- 1. Min-frequency (default $\geq 3-5$).** Discards phantom typo diacritic forms (*šmo@8*, *nišam@10*, *žbog@9*) that would otherwise turn a safe ASCII form into a *spuriously ambiguous* key. The filter removes $\sim 86\%$ of ambiguous keys ($\approx 33k \rightarrow \approx 2k$) with no recall loss — genuine rare words occur dozens of times — and shrinks the dictionary (edit error $0.59\% \rightarrow 0.36\%$; 33 MB $\rightarrow \sim 5$ MB).
- 2. Frequency.** When a count is available, candidates are ranked by descending frequency; the "most-frequent wins" prior is correct even on an alphabetically sorted source file.
- 3. Case.** A form seen only capitalized is treated as a proper noun and dropped (precision-first; otherwise *Mozes* \rightarrow *mozes* would block the frequent *možeš*). A key whose only candidate equals itself goes into a compact invariant set (needed only by the gate), not into the main index.

Per-language recipes. Croatian — the raw frequency list (OpenSubtitles) contains both *država* and the bare *država*, which would poison the index, so it is filtered through a clean Hunspell hr that keeps only validated words (drops *država*, keeps *sto/što*); recall rises monotonically with lexicon size: 50k \rightarrow 11,338 keys/61.5%, full \rightarrow 76,116/79.6%, then up to 156,922. Serbian — the only Hunspell sr is contaminated (it lists bare non-words such as *moze/rec* as valid stems), so it cannot be used as a filter; the source is a curated diacritic word list (ekavian *reč/beh/način* with srWaC frequencies), with two adjustments: bare valid homographs (*da*, *sto*, *kuca*) are injected as candidates so they are not over-restored, and an ekavian protect-list covers forms missing from the ijekavian Hunspell (fixing e.g. *gde* \rightarrow *gđe*). Bosnian — grown 11,350 \rightarrow 114,092 keys via the full bs frequency list plus an hr-Hunspell filter.

Insight. Diacritic-bearing forms need no Hunspell filter at all: because shaving *removes* diacritics, the presence of *č/ć/š/ž/đ* in a frequency list already proves the form genuine. Only diacritic-free homographs are run through Hunspell. The lossiness of shaving doubles as a free quality filter.

9.4 The resolve table (Lever 1)

For each ambiguous key (whose bare form is itself a candidate) a winner is chosen by an **independent** frequency prior — Leipzig wiki/news, deliberately *not* the dictionary's source (OpenSubtitles), to avoid contamination. $\text{conf} = \text{freq}(\text{accented}) / \sum \text{freq}(\text{candidates})$; the policy is GO if $\text{conf} \geq \theta$ (0.95), else HOLD. A compact `bald-winner` map plus a numeric guard is baked into the pack. Decontaminating the prior is critical: using the dictionary's own source as the prior inflates confidence on exactly the homographs where it should be cautious. The Serbian table has 29,682 keys (columns `rank · bald · winner · confidence · policy · numeric_guard · candidates`); at $\theta=0.95$ it splits into 8,680 GO / 21,002 HOLD. A scan of 351,994 sentences found that only 1,396 GO rules ever fire (3,754 never fire — a dead tail), so the shipped Serbian table is trimmed 5,150→1,396 with no recall change. The trim was *measured*, not guessed: of the 1,396 kept, 896 fire only rarely and a blind "top-500" cut would have discarded them. After rebuilding all three through one builder on a comparable Leipzig prior: **sr 1,396 · hr 578 · bs 481** (a clean rebuild of Serbian yields 497 GO rules — in the hr/bs band; the larger shipped count was an artifact of a richer original prior).

9.5 The PolyType product — an adaptive input aid

PolyType is a macOS menu-bar app. Its base function is a layout corrector (it repairs words typed in the wrong layout, `ghbdtñ` → `привет`, as you type), out of which the *dešišavanje* feature grew from the research. Design philosophy: **invisibility** (the tool lives between thought and fingers; if it is noticed, it has erred), **trust over aggression** (one wrong "corrected the correct" erodes trust more than ten misses; in doubtful cases it stays silent), an **explainable deterministic core** (language statistics, no heavy ML on the hot path), and a **local personal profile** (nothing leaves the device).

The pair philosophy. System switchers work like a "revolver": one combination cycles through all layouts, and with three or more languages autocorrect multiplies false triggers. Observation: a bilingual person works with a *pair* of languages at any moment, not all at once. The solution — a key is bound to a **pair** (the Latin member ↔ the other member), not to a language; auto-detection always compares only the two languages of the active pair. So even with three or more languages autocorrect stays binary, and false triggers are exactly as few as with two — which revolver OS switchers cannot deliver in principle. **Language identity** is coded by a triple of "glyph + colour + sound" (e.g. Я, Ё, Ī), the same in the menu-bar indicator, in the pair rows of the menu, and in the field-border flash on switching — the language is recognized without reading the letter. For a pair of Serbo-Croatian layouts, a double-tap performs a linguistic Cyrillic↔Latin transliteration (`љ↔lj`, `њ↔nj`, `џ↔dž`) with digraph handling and an exception list at morpheme joints (*nadživeti*, *injekcija*, *konjugacija*). The *dešišavanje* layer is enabled as a separate checkbox and fires at the word boundary after the layout decision; reverting is by backspace, with a special sound, without disturbing the layout.

9.6 The SlipWay product — a clipboard manager

SlipWay is a clipboard manager (a fork of DrPaste). It keeps a lossless clipboard history (text, images, files with source metadata), applies deterministic transforms with no network (pseudo-fonts, transliteration, and among them *dešišavanje* through the same library — streaming `restoreText` for a whole text). The key gesture — hold `⌘V`, scroll history and transforms with the arrows, release to paste. The engine-integration form is identical: lazy dictionary loading, a `str` → `str` contract with no network and no state — the same contract that makes the engine embeddable both in an IME and in the library.

9.7 Feedback and privacy (designed, not implemented)

The current version runs **locally only**, with no backend or crowdsourcing (the author's decision, June 2026; in the off state there is zero network activity). A designed-but-unimplemented learning loop would capture **autocorrect reverts** by backspace within a short keystroke window. The clean signal is "the user undid *my* edit" (three rejection types: touched too much → a signal to the gate; restored the wrong candidate → a signal to frequencies/context; did nothing while the user added the diacritic themselves → the most valuable signal, hitting the coverage bottleneck directly). A quarantine gives instant personalization without sending anything out; the globally new goes out only through the gate, OFF by default, with an explicit display of what would leave, and only on independent confirmation from different users. Backspace as a "free mode detector" is a direct consequence of bimodality (§3.5).

9.8 Product metrics (each pack on its own corpus)

The numbers below are each measured on the pack's default corpus and are **not comparable across languages**: hr on clean Tatoeba (96.1%) is higher than sr on the forum (93.7%) not because the Croatian engine is better, but because clean text is easier than forum text. Only Fig. 10 serves the cross-language

comparison.

Fig. 15. Recall per pack on its default corpus (resolve ON). Different registers and corpora — this is not a cross-language ranking (see Fig. 10 for the controlled comparison). Each bar is labelled with the corpus, register, and edit-precision (EP: sr 99.6%, hr 99.98%, bs 99.9%), to rule out a false reading as a ranking of languages.

Summary of the shipped packs (product numbers, NOT to be compared across languages):

Language (ISO)	Keys	Resolve	Recall (corpus)	Edit-prec.	OOV
Bosnian (bs)	114,092	481	94.9% Tatoeba [93.7, 96.1] · 91.6% klix.ba UGC [89.4, 93.7]	99.5-100%	<6%
Croatian (hr)	156,922	578	96.1% Tatoeba [95.6, 96.6] · 95.1% Wikipedia [94.4, 95.8] · 91.3% chat [88.9, 93.8]	99.5-100%	<4%
Serbian (sr)	156,931	1,396	93.9% real šišana [92.9, 94.7] · 93.7% forum	~99.6%	—
Montenegrin (cnr)			limited, via the Serbian pack (š/ž pass through); see §11.2		

Honest edit-precision: sr 99.6% / hr 99.98% / bs ≥99.9% (an upper bound, 0 errors on the sample — the renderer was fixed not to display a false "100%" if the true value is lower). Confidence intervals — a cluster (document) bootstrap, B=2000, fixed seed; all validation corpora are independent of the dictionary's training source.

10. The research ↔ implementation loop

The honest denominator for recall is **fixable words** (the gold is produced by taking accented text, shaving it, then restoring), not all words. On a 6,005-post two-forum corpus (14,341 fixable words) the production trajectory below shows how each lever was found and why it mattered:

Step	Recall	Wrong	What it taught
engine, honest denominator	73.5%	0.21%	gap = 12.7pp ambiguous-in-passthrough + 13.6pp OOV
+ dictionary 45k→100k	78.9%	0.25%	+5.4pp for 2.3× size; Zipf makes coverage expensive
their bigrams (80/20) on the bucket	93.2% (bucket)	—	left-only suffices (left+right = 92.9%, worse)
decontaminated unigram prior on the bucket	95.4% (bucket)	—	a static prior beats a low-data bigram at zero runtime cost
+ resolve table v1 (rank-HOLD)	80.2%	0.26%	only +1.3pp — error mass ≠ traffic mass
+ confidence policy (conf≥0.95)	90.0%	0.31%	+9.8pp recall for +0.05pp wrong
+ cap-250k dictionary	93.2%	—	shipped operating point
+ minfreq=3 (4.9 MB)	93.7%	0.36%	size/quality knee
full flat lexicon	95.1%	0.59%→0.36%	research ceiling (~196 MB RAM, undeployable)

Especially telling is the "table as-is in the file" step: it initially gave only +1.3pp (78.9→80.2), because the high-frequency ambiguous forms (*sto*, *ce*, *da*, *vas*, *nas*, *ovde*) were conservatively set to HOLD — and they carry almost all the ambiguous traffic. Lifting HOLD where the decontaminated prior is confident (conf ≥ 0.95) freed +9.8pp at a cost of only +0.05pp error — because in the chat context the prior is right ~99.7% of the time. This is the numerical illustration of "error mass ≠ traffic mass": safe rules (GO) are numerous but low-traffic; all the recall is locked behind a wall of HOLD on a few frequent forms.

Minfreq sweep (sr): 1→808k keys/25 MB/94.1%/0.38%; 2→180k/5.6 MB/93.8%/0.37%; 3→157k/4.9 MB/93.7%/0.36% (shipped); 5→131k/4.0 MB/93.5%/0.36%. The 1→2 step cuts size 4.5× for -0.3pp recall.

Capacity / RAM curve (capability ≠ deployability):

Configuration	Keys	Disk	RAM (est.)	Recall
cap-100k	40k	1.5 MB	~few MB	90.0%
cap-250k (shipped)	108k	3.5 MB	~15-20 MB	93.2%
cap-500k	237k	7 MB	~40 MB	94.3%
full (~1M)	1.1M	33 MB	~196 MB	95.1%

The full flat index reproduces the research ceiling (95.1%) but is not shippable in a menu-bar keyboard; the top quarter of the lexicon by frequency gives +3.2pp for +2 MB — the "sweet spot" for a compact interceptor. A note on method: the early conclusion "popular words don't help" was an artifact of sorting — rank was computed alphabetically, not by frequency; rebuilding by frequency gave the opposite, correct picture. Reaching 95% on-device is a data-structure task (mmap or a DAWG/FST runtime), not a data task.

Left vs right context (held-out 80/20, the *sto/što* bucket): baseline 0% → left context 93.2% → left+right 92.9%. Right context does not help — it even hurts slightly. Left context and the unigram prior are **substitutes, not complements** (their joint contribution barely exceeds either alone, +0.1pp). The consequence is direct: the keyboard runtime needs no deferred parse (waiting for the word on the right), no lag and no flicker. Context is the last small step to the ceiling, not the main engine; the dictionary and the prior do the heavy lifting.

Engine review — five defects of the original implementation (worth recording as failure modes): (1) invariant keys were discarded, making the language check falsely negative — fixed with a compact invariant set; (2) lowercasing without a proper-noun branch let a name borrow a common word's rank — fixed with a lowercase-only index; (3) building from a word list ignored frequencies, breaking the prior on an unsorted file — fixed; (4) JSON + dictionary lookup needs a DAWG/mmap for the full lexicon; (5) mixed-case input should pass through.

Stopping arithmetic (choosing the deployment target). With ~3 fixable words per message, 90% recall is a miss roughly every one-or-two messages; ~98% is a miss about every 15 ("always works"); the step from 98% to 99.5% is imperceptible to the user. So the deployment target is ~98% via a web-scale lexicon, then stop — a concrete instance of "capability ≠ deployability".

11. Discussion

11.1 The macro-language framing

The object of the work is the Serbo-Croatian macro-language (ISO 639-3 *hbs*), not three isolated languages. This

framing is not cosmetic: it explains why we cover exactly three of the four standard varieties and why a single engine serves them. The formulation is two-part and deliberately cautious. On the computational side, diacritic restoration is unified for the whole macro-language and realized by a shared core — proven by the symmetric matrix. On the other hand, inter-variety differences are real (ekavian vs ijekavian, the frequency of individual letters, the original presence or absence of a resolve table) and are encapsulated in the language-pack data. The continuum framing does not erase the varieties' differences — it only claims that, at the level of our task, they express themselves as data parameters, not as different algorithms.

11.2 Montenegrin as a boundary case

The macro-language has a fourth standard variety — Montenegrin (cnr) — which we deliberately do not add as a separate pack; and the reason is itself a result. We state the status neutrally: Montenegrin is a member of the Serbo-Croatian macro-language (SIL ISO 639-3); the separate standard took shape recently (a 2007 constitution after 2006 independence; the ISO code `cnr` was assigned in 2017, with the first request that same year rejected for insufficient evidence of difference from Serbian), and its distinctive orthography introduces the letters *ś* and *ź*, politically loaded as identity markers. Our exclusion criterion is operational, not evaluative: we pass no judgment on the language's status, but ask only one thing — does Montenegrin present a computationally separate diacritic-restoration task.

Empirically — it does not. Typed *ś* and *ź* pass through the engine untouched (100%, 22 of 22): they are invariant to shaving, since they do not decompose into *č/ć/š/ž/đ*, the key turns out non-ASCII, and `restore` returns nil. Shaved *ś/ź* collapse into the same bare form as Serbian (*šutra* → *sutra*) and are resolved by the shared dictionary. The alternative hypothesis — that a separate *ś*→*š* rule is needed — we tested and rejected: adding it would only create false collisions. The two observed errors (*ženica* → *ženica*) proved to be not an *ś/ź* specificity but a manifestation of the shared homograph tail also present in plain Serbian. The conclusion, important for the overarching thesis: the boundary politics draws between the varieties, at the level of diacritic restoration, **does not computationally exist** — Montenegrin is operationally Serbian for this task. This is the macro-language thesis in miniature, stated in a technical rather than a political register.

11.3 Generalization — honest about the limits

The core is language-agnostic within the **diacritic-stripping family** — Latin-script languages whose diacritics are stripped into ASCII: Czech, Slovak, Polish, Slovenian, Romanian, Hungarian, Turkish (with a small locale fix for the *ı/i* pair), German (via expanding the digraphs *ä*→*ae*, *ß*→*ss*). This is not a theoretical claim but an architecturally prepared generalization: three languages already run on one core without changing it, and the mechanism for adding a fourth — data plus profile — is described and tested. But there is an honest limit, and we do not cross it. Cross-script romanizations — Arabizi, Greeklish, Cyrillic translit — belong to a different problem class: a change of script, a many-to-many mapping with far greater ambiguity, and the current abstraction does not model them. We mark them as an adjacent task and a direction for future work. The hardest *in-scope* edge is Vietnamese (tone + vowel marks, high ambiguity → a dictionary-only approach is weak): that is exactly where the thesis is tested to breaking, and a negative result there is as valuable as a positive one.

11.4 Methodological insight

The irreversibility of shaving works as a free dictionary-quality filter: a form containing a diacritic (*č/ć/š/ž/đ*) in a frequency list is genuine by construction, since shaving removes diacritics — so its presence proves the form was not generated by shaving noise. This let us pour in large frequency lists directly, passing only the diacritic-free forms through a lexical validator, and thereby grow coverage without losing precision (cf. §6.8, §9.3).

11.5 The four "series theorems"

1. **Coverage ≠ quality.** Precision is bounded by the quality of the dictionary *tail*, not its size; naive growth imports noise faster than signal (87% of the full lexicon is `freq<5` noise).
2. **Error mass ≠ traffic mass.** A rank-based HOLD adds +1.3pp, a confidence-based one +9.8pp; error is concentrated in a few frequent forms, so guards must be keyed to confidence, not rank.
3. **Capability ≠ deployability.** The 95.1% ceiling costs ~196 MB RAM and is not shippable; the operating point is a deployment parameter, not a property of the method.
4. **Left context and the unigram prior are substitutes, not complements.** Right context is unnecessary; the runtime needs no deferred parse.

11.6 Methodology lessons

1. A verification search before every "first" — prior art (Ivković) nearly turned a claimed novelty into a desk-reject.
2. The denominator decides everything — "9% recall" of all words and "73.5%" of fixable words describe the same system.
3. Compare against a strong baseline, not against zero (bigrams vs passthrough).
4. Error mass \neq traffic mass: confidence guards, not rank guards.
5. Frequency data about a shaved language is itself infected by the phenomenon — decontaminate.
6. Never transcribe data "from memory" — an incident with a hand-built witness set nearly corrupted an experiment with invalid witnesses.
7. The gate belongs in the measurement instrument as well as in the product.
8. Prefer published corpora (reproducibility, ethics); self-collect only what does not otherwise exist.
9. Move bulk data out of a browser in delimited chunks via `console.log`.
10. A static prior beats a low-data bigram at zero runtime cost.
11. Control confounds (register, dictionary size) *before* attributing a gap to language or algorithm — the core of the symmetric experiment.
12. Measure, don't assume — including about why two numbers differ (a "stale counts" premise turned out to be a property of the corpus, not the run).

A note on figures. Results fall into four blocks that sit on **different axes** and must never be mixed: (A) the controlled cross-language matrix (recall by register, three varieties, resolve OFF, CIs; Fig. 10); (B) the resolve lever (OFF→ON slope per variety, + Δ pp, precision held; Fig. 12); (C) coverage trajectories (recall vs log dictionary size, monotonic; Fig. 11); (D) per-pack deployment recall, each on its own register (Fig. 15). In particular, block-D numbers are different registers and are **not** comparable across languages; they must not be placed next to the block-A comparison.

12. Reproducibility

All reported numbers live in a machine-readable `results_aggregate.tsv`. Raw corpora are not committed (size + terms of use); reproducibility runs through the scripts plus a seeded bootstrap plus the aggregate TSV. Wiki/news cells use Leipzig sentences (Serbian transliterated to Latin via `cyr2lat_sr`); Tatoeba dumps provide clean sentences (CC-BY). Core commands:

```
# Confidence interval for any cell (document-level cluster bootstrap):
recall_ci.py --code sr --corpus <doc.jsonl> [--no-resolve] [--seed 12345]

# Real-error track (fetches SentiComments.SR on demand):
eval_senticomments.py --code sr [--no-resolve]

# Baselines (do-nothing, most-frequent):
baselines.py --code sr --corpus <doc.jsonl>

# Full dictionary rebuild:
filter_hunspell.py → build_deshishana.py → build_resolve_table.py → inject_resolve.py

# Register × language matrix:
build_corpus_matrix.py
for c in sr hr bs; do for g in wiki news tatoeba; do
  recall_ci.py --code $c --no-resolve --corpus cell_${c}_${g}.jsonl --label $c-$g
done; done
```

Tool set: `build_deshishana.py`, `build_resolve_table.py/build_resolve_any.py`, `inject_resolve.py`, `filter_hunspell.py`, `filter_leipzig.py`, `cyr2lat_sr.py`, `eval_deshishana.py`, `ablate_deshishana.py`, `recall_ci.py`, `baselines.py`, `eval_senticomments.py`, `build_corpus_matrix.py`, `test_montenegrin_szz.py`.

Code and data availability. All repository references in this document are pinned to an immutable commit, so they remain valid even if files are later renamed. The numbers were read from `ioDiacritics` commit `be745a653605f6934ea127f1c2c909e242055b5d` (main, 2026-06-13): <https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics/tree/be745a653605f6934ea127f1c2c909e242055b5d>. Relative to that commit: the engine (Swift core + C++17 port), the build/evaluation tool set (`tools/`), the per-experiment reports and corpus-matrix notes (`research/`), the paper-facing snapshot (`RESEARCH.md`), and the data-licensing audit (`docs/DATA_LICENSE_AUDIT.md`); the package is MIT. Runnable demos (SwiftUI for macOS and C++ Dear ImGui for Windows/macOS/Linux) are in `ioDiacritics-Demos` at commit `bf392d353fe33fc1913cf5eea613886ed4bd0cdf` (<https://github.com/ilya000/ioDiacritics-Demos/tree/bf392d353fe33fc1913cf5eea613886ed4bd0cdf>). For a citable identifier, this exact state will additionally be archived as a tagged release with a Zenodo DOI

10.5281/zenodo.20688770. SlipWay derives from DrPaste (<https://github.com/ilya000/DrPaste>).

13. Data provenance and licenses

The ioDiacritics engine code is MIT. The bundled dictionaries are **generated artifacts from mixed third-party sources**, not "MIT-only data"; provenance is documented separately, and a clean-MIT release can ship code and tools without the bundled dictionaries (the numbers are reproducible from scripts plus a seeded bootstrap).

Source	License	Role
Serbian curated word list (turanjanin/serbian-language-tools)	MIT	sr lexicon provenance
redi (clarinsi/redi)	Apache-2.0	prior-art restoration system (hr/sr/sl)
FrequencyWords / OpenSubtitles (hermitdave)	code MIT / content CC BY-SA 4.0	hr/bs frequency lists
Leipzig Wortschatz	CC BY	independent prior for resolve + validation
Tatoeba	CC BY 2.0	clean validation sentences (hrv/bos)
Hunspell hr/sr (LibreOffice)	LGPL / SISSL	lexicon filter
SETimes.SR	—	news gold eval
SentiComments.SR	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	real-error gold (NonCommercial)

Practical release posture: a LICENSE (MIT) for code, a NOTICE file documenting the separate data provenance, and — where a clean-MIT artifact is needed — code and tools published without the bundled dictionaries.

14. Conclusion

We have shown that diacritic-free writing in Serbo-Croatian is a stable written register, not corruption: it is graded by genre, discrete (bimodal), stable over time, and orthogonal to standardness. The inverse task — diacritic restoration — is solvable on-device by a dictionary with a frequency prior, at an edit-precision of about 99.6–99.98%, with no neural model at runtime for the error that real input actually presents. And, most importantly: under a controlled comparison the three varieties of the macro-language are indistinguishable, and a single engine with no core change serves the whole continuum — the differences that looked linguistic turned out to be data parameters. The Montenegrin case pushes this thesis to its limit, showing that the political boundary between varieties has no computational existence at the level of our task. The method is embodied in an open-source library (ioDiacritics, MIT) and in two applications (PolyType, SlipWay) that demonstrate two modes of using one engine.

We frame the overall contribution along three dimensions. **Sociolinguistic:** a large single-method quantification of registers, decontamination of priors, documented bimodality, the *đ* effect, orthogonality to standardness, and a decade-later replication of Ivković. **Computational:** an open task inventory, decomposition of the residual (0.49%; 13/397 forms), the structural impossibility of correct behaviour on code-switched input without a gate with a wild-data confirmation, and four methodological theorems (coverage ≠ quality; error mass ≠ traffic mass; capability ≠ deployability; left context and the prior are substitutes). **Systemic:** the research ↔ implementation loop and the symmetric matrix showing the cross-language gap is coverage, not language. It remains to collect the writers' own perspective (Study 1b, §4) and to delimit the method's transfer to the rest of the diacritic-stripping family — which we set out as the next steps. Wording throughout is deliberately conservative: "we provide evidence that..." rather than "we prove...", and "an LLM is unnecessary for the measured residual" rather than "an LLM is never needed".

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Note on the bibliography: the principal references (Batanović 2020; Ivković 2013, 2015; Krstev et al. 2018; Ljubešić et al. 2016; Magner 2001; Šantić et al. 2009) were verified against publisher and ACL/ELRA sources; the typological extensions (Novák & Siklósi 2015; Petrică et al. 2014; Pham et al. 2017; Iftene & Trandabăţ 2009) are given for context in §11.3. The Hentschel (1998) entry is cited secondarily and its exact bibliographic details are to be confirmed by DOI before archiving the release.

Appendix A. Figures

All fifteen figures appear at their respective sections and are listed here for convenience. The palette is unified and safe for greyscale printing and for colour-blind readers; the variety colours (sr/hr/bs) are consistent across panels. **Critical rule:** blocks A/B/C/D sit on different axes and are never mixed on one (in particular, block-D product numbers — Fig. 15 — must not be placed next to the block-A matrix — Fig. 10 — for a cross-language comparison).

- **Fig. 1** (§3.3) — register gradient: % shaved rises news→IT forum.
- **Fig. 2** (§3.5) — bimodality vs. binomial null: a discrete writing mode.
- **Fig. 3** (§3.6) — the đ effect: ~5× over-represented among selective omissions.
- **Fig. 4** (§6.1–6.2) — shaving map + double-encoded reverse index.
- **Fig. 5** (§6.4) — inventory by types vs. tokens: 1.25% types / 9–14% tokens.
- **Fig. 6** (§6.5) — error concentration: 50% of error mass in 13 forms, 90% in 397.
- **Fig. 7** (§6.7) — baseline ladder: the unigram prior does the heavy lifting.
- **Fig. 8** (§6.8) — minfreq knee: size↔quality, precision bounded by tail quality.
- **Fig. 9** (§7) — code-switching and the gate (D4): 166 corruptions → 0.
- **Fig. 10** (§8.2) — symmetric matrix, block A: three languages indistinguishable under control.
- **Fig. 11** (§8.3) — coverage trajectory, block C: monotonic growth (log axis).
- **Fig. 12** (§8.4) — resolve lever OFF→ON, block B: +8.5...+9.8pp symmetric.
- **Fig. 13** (§9.1) — system architecture: one engine, data-not-code language packs.
- **Fig. 14** (§9.2) — runtime decision flow of `restore()`: precision-first.
- **Fig. 15** (§9.8) — product metrics, block D: each bar on its own corpus, not a cross-language ranking.

Appendix B. Study 1b questionnaire (planned)

The questionnaire is designed, but the survey has not yet been run (§4). Below is the structure: 14 questions, ~3 minutes, neutral Serbo-Croatian Latin, Google Forms, anonymous, no email collection, with a consent checkbox. Under each question the parenthetical is the testable claim (not copied into the form itself).

Title: *Kako pišemo na računaru i telefonu — kratka anketa (3 minuta)*. The intro explains that the survey is anonymous, studies how people write in Latin with diacritics (č, ć, š, ž, đ) or without them, and that "there are no right or wrong answers".

Block 1 — layouts and devices. Q1: which keyboards you use for your native language (physical with our letters / physical without them / phone with our layout / phone on another layout) — *the "keyboard environment" predictor*. Q2: on which device you most often write — *device control*.

Block 2 — writing mode. Q3: how often you use diacritics in informal writing (always ... never) — *the main variable, bimodality expected*. Q4: the same for formal writing — *register gradient at the individual level*. Q5: if you sometimes write without diacritics, why (faster / not on the layout / habit / understood anyway / autocorrect interferes / other) — *separates the infrastructural reason from the normative one*.

Block 3 — awareness. Q6: do you notice the absence of diacritics in others' text. Q7: does it bother you when others write without diacritics. Q8: do you consider writing without diacritics "illiterate" or "just a different way" — *the central sociolinguistic measurement of status*.

Block 4 — autocorrect and reverting. Q9: does the device restore diacritics by itself. Q10: how useful a reliable, error-free diacritic auto-substitution would be — *demand for the feature*. Q11: what you do on a wrong autocorrect (revert with backspace / leave it / turn autocorrect off / hasn't happened) — *the precision-first justification via revert frequency*.

Block 5 — demographics (opt.). Q12: native language (Serbian / Croatian / Bosnian / Montenegrin / other) — *the by-variety cut for the macro-language framing*. Q13: age. Q14: an open comment field.

Target N: ≥150–200 responses (≥50 per variety) for stable percentages with a cut; realistic in 2–3 weeks on forums and Reddit.

Appendix C. Software version history (condensed)

ioDiacritics (library): 0.4.0 → 0.5.0 → 0.6.0 (bs to hr level) → 0.7.0 (hr to sr level) → 0.8.0 (three BCS packs aligned) → 0.8.2 (sr-resolve trim 5,150→1,396) → 0.9.0 (C++17 port) → 0.9.1 (honest reliability passports — removed a false "100% edit-precision"). The paper's number snapshot is commit `be745a6` (2026-06-13).

PolyType (application): 0.10.2 → 0.10.3 → 0.10.7 (migration to the library) → 0.10.13. Key milestones: multilingual pairs; mixed-script pairs; a configurable conversion key; Serbo-Croatian Cyrillic↔Latin transliteration by double-tap; extraction of the *dešišavanje* layer into the shared library; language identity by "glyph + colour + sound".

SlipWay: a fork of DrPaste; integration of the engine as one of the buffer's deterministic transforms via the `str` → `str` contract.

All numbers were produced by scripts on open data and cross-checked against the aggregate results table; the raw resolution tables are summarized statistically rather than reproduced row-by-row and remain regenerable from the documented pipeline. Preprint v7 · 14 June 2026.